

Heal Talk

Endo

Talk

Minimal Invasive Endodontics

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A successful root canal procedure increases the likelihood that the tooth will continue to function normally within the mouth for a significant amount of time. After endodontic treatment, the lifetime of a tooth is dependent on the amount of residual tissue and healing. However, there are many other factors that impact endodontic outcomes such as the quality of the restoration and structural integrity of the tooth after root canal preparation. The remaining dental structure and restorations have a significant impact on the long-term viability of an endodontically treated tooth. Minimally invasive endodontics (MIE) is an endodontic technique that aims to maintain as much of the healthy coronal, cervical, and radicular tooth structure as possible. This innovative kind of root canal therapy, known as minimally invasive endodontics (MIE), takes a different approach that focuses on minimizing structural alterations after treatment. Treatment and prevention of pulpal diseases and apical periodontitis, as well as preserving as much good tissue as possible, are all part of the MIE method, which is safe, accurate, and time-saving. Endodontic procedures are becoming less invasive because of the development of new materials and technology, such as cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) scans, advanced microscopes, unique access designs, and inventive access cavities. Access opening, root canal cleaning and shaping, and surgical endodontics are all possible applications for MIE in endodontic treatment. The objective of new-age endodontics is minimum intervention. A favourable outcome with minimally invasive treatment may be achieved while preserving the tooth's natural structure with careful case selection. The concept of minimally invasive endodontics calls for the treatment and prevention of pulpal pathoses and apical periodontitis, while causing the least amount of change to the dental hard tissues. This preserves the strength and function of the endodontically treated tooth with the intent that it will last the patient's lifetime.

Just as in medicine, the dental surgeon treating endodontic disease must develop new skills and dexterity in order to adapt to a limited working environment within the confines of the pulpal space. These skills include working with new instruments and irrigants for cleaning the system; utilising

advanced imaging modalities and computer software for demonstrating both the complexities of the root canal system and improving the accuracy of techniques; employing increased magnification and lighting for visualising the pulpal space as well as applying new materials that enhance the prognosis for restoring structure and retaining the natural dentition.

Preserving structural integrity

Some of the ideas in the way dentistry has been practiced over the past century have recently undergone a paradigm shift. The tooth's residual structural integrity is a critical component in determining prognosis in terms of future function after restoration. The purpose of all restorative therapies, notably in endodontics, is to maintain strength and stiffness that resists structural deformation. For example, extension for prevention is no longer found to be widely accepted, as it requires removal of the sound and intact tooth structure for only a potential chance of a future benefit. Understanding the biomechanical behaviour of dentin as the weakest link in any restorative system is essential if we are to avoid causing more harm to it.

There have been cases when endodontically treated teeth were extracted because of inadequate repair of the dental structure. It has been found that a tooth with extensive enamel and dentin loss performs much worse than an undamaged tooth when it comes to the capacity to bear occlusal and functional forces. Reduced access preparation diameter by half resulted in the operator removing four times less tooth structure in MIE compared to a standard preparation. A higher density of dentin boosted the tooth's tensile and fracture strength, making it more resistant to breakage. Based on logical reasoning, the preservation of maximal dentine mass during access cavity preparation and root canal shaping is of utmost importance; to date, no manufactured substance can effectively compensate for the lost dentinal tissue because of its unique features and traits. Endodontic therapy can also affect the lifespan of endodontic treatment, tooth rehabilitation, and biomechanics during oral function. Several factors and clinical judgments must be followed while recovering endodontically treated teeth. The choice of fiberglass posts and restorative materials is influenced by several criteria,